

**KEY ASPECTS OF ENHANCING THE ROLE OF
PROSECUTOR’S OFFICE IN THE PROCESS OF DIGITAL
TRANSFORMATION OF THE STATE**

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Annotation:

The article explores the role of the prosecutor’s office of Uzbekistan in the digital transformation of the state within the framework of the “Digital Uzbekistan – 2030” Strategy. It emphasizes the need to introduce modern information technologies, strengthen digital competencies among staff, and develop a specialized strategy for prosecutorial digitalization. Special attention is given to combating cybercrime, with recommendations to establish dedicated prosecutorial units and adopt international best practices. The study highlights that strengthening the prosecutor’s office in this process will ensure legality, enhance public trust, and support the country’s digital economy.

Keywords:

Prosecutor’s office, digital transformation, Digital Uzbekistan – 2030, e-governance, cybercrime, legality, public trust.

In the modern era of global digitalization, the transformation of public administration has become an integral element of the development of any state. Digital transformation affects all areas of state activity, including the law enforcement system, in which the prosecutor’s office plays an important role

in ensuring legality and public order. In the context of implementing the “Digital Uzbekistan – 2030” Strategy, the study of the role of the prosecutor’s office in the process of the country’s digital transformation acquires particular relevance.

It should be emphasized that the digital transformation of public authorities is a complex process of introducing modern information and communication technologies into the system of public administration, aimed at improving the efficiency of state bodies and the quality of services provided. Digital transformation is not limited to the simple automation of existing processes but implies a fundamental revision of public administration mechanisms in the context of digital reality. As K. Schwab noted, digital transformation is characterized by the fusion of technologies that blur the boundaries between the physical, digital, and biological spheres [1]. This phenomenon has a significant impact on all state institutions, including the law enforcement system, and in particular, the prosecutor’s office.

It is well known that the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. DP–6079 of October 5, 2020 approved the “Digital Uzbekistan – 2030” Strategy, which envisions the large-scale modernization of public administration on the basis of digital technologies. This strategy is a comprehensive plan for the development of information technologies in the country, aimed at creating the conditions for transition to a digital economy, improving the quality of life of citizens, and enhancing the investment climate.

As a key element of the system for ensuring legality, the prosecutor’s office of Uzbekistan faces the necessity of adapting to the new conditions of digital reality. In particular, according to E. Pavlova, digitalization is an inevitable process that penetrates all spheres of social life. The prosecutor’s office is also subject to the influence of digitalization, which significantly simplifies the process of protecting the rights and legitimate interests of citizens. However, since this area is still at the stage of development, there remain problems that require solutions [2].

Improving the process of digital transformation of the prosecutor's office of the Republic of Uzbekistan represents a complex and multifaceted process that covers various aspects of the activities of the prosecutorial system. Given the scope and significance of the "Digital Uzbekistan – 2030" Strategy for the country's development, it is advisable to expand the participation of the prosecutor's office in its implementation and broaden its powers in exercising oversight over its execution.

At this point, it should be noted that for the effective implementation of digital prosecutorial oversight, it is essential to introduce modern information technologies into the prosecutor's office, strengthen its staff with employees possessing knowledge and skills in the field of information and communication technologies, and, in short, carry out the digital transformation of the prosecutor's office. Fully supporting M. Boboev's proposal to consolidate and improve the regulatory documents adopted on the digital transformation of the prosecutor's office and, on this basis, to develop a "Strategy for the Digital Transformation of the Prosecutor's Office until 2030," it should be emphasized that, in our view, the effective implementation of this strategy will mark the period of 2030–2050 as the era of introducing artificial intelligence into the activities of the prosecutor's office [3].

Within the structure of the Prosecutor General's Office of the Russian Federation, there is the Main Directorate for Supervision over the Execution of Federal Legislation, which includes the Department for Supervision over the Implementation of Laws in the Field of Information Technology and Information Protection [4]. One of the main tasks of this department is to ensure the enforcement of laws in the areas of information technology, information systems, and information protection by federal executive bodies, the Investigative Committee of the Russian Federation, federal-level supervisory (inspection) bodies, their officials, as well

as by the governing bodies and leaders of commercial and non-commercial organizations. It also ensures that legal acts adopted by these entities comply with the law [5].

In conclusion, the establishment of a Department for Assisting in the Supervision of the Implementation of Legislation in the Field of Information and Communication Technologies within the structure of the Prosecutor General's Office of the Republic of Uzbekistan would represent an important step in ensuring legality and public order during the country's digital transformation process. This, in turn, would help create favorable conditions for the development of the digital economy in Uzbekistan, improve the quality of public services, and strengthen citizens' trust in state services.

It should also be noted that in the process of the state's digital transformation, the role of the prosecutor's office is of particular importance in combating cybercrime. Alongside numerous advantages, modern technologies bring new challenges for the law enforcement system, requiring the adaptation of existing mechanisms and the establishment of new structures to effectively counter crimes in the digital environment. According to Statista's Market Insights, the global damage caused by cybercrime is projected to reach 13.82 trillion U.S. dollars by 2028 [6].

The above figures clearly demonstrate the scale of the negative impact of cybercrime on the global economy. Cybercrime not only leads to financial losses but also poses a serious threat to national security, disrupts the activities of state bodies and non-governmental organizations, and encroaches on citizens' personal data and rights. This, in turn, requires the prosecutor's office to deeply master modern information and communication technologies, develop new methodologies for collecting and analyzing digital evidence, and strengthen international cooperation.

In the context of digital transformation, the issue of establishing specialized units within the prosecutorial system to combat cybercrime is of particular importance. International experience shows the effectiveness of such an approach. For instance, the U.S. Department of Justice operates the Computer Crime and Intellectual Property Section (CCIPS), which specializes in investigating computer crimes and protecting intellectual property in the digital environment. The main tasks of this section include preventing and stopping computer crimes and intellectual property offenses through investigation and prosecution, guiding investigators and prosecutors in the proper collection of electronic evidence, and providing technical and legal advice and assistance to security service officers and prosecutors both in the United States and worldwide [7].

In Germany, due to the growing number of cybercrime cases and the increasing complexity of cases handled by prosecutors, special investigative units have been established, such as the Central Unit for Combating Cybercrime in Bavaria, which enables effective action against new types of crimes in the digital environment [8].

Similar units also exist within the prosecutorial systems of Spain, Serbia, Singapore, and Romania.

In our opinion, in the era of digitalization, protecting the rights and freedoms of citizens in the information space is becoming one of the state's primary tasks. The prosecutor's office must occupy a leading position in ensuring legality in the digital environment.

We believe that the establishment of a special department within the structure of the Prosecutor General's Office would bring a number of advantages. First, it would ensure a unified approach to coordinating the activities of law enforcement agencies in combating cybercrime and increase the effectiveness of such efforts. Second, as the prosecutor's office has the authority to supervise the

implementation of laws, it would be able to effectively monitor compliance with legality in conducting operational-search measures and investigative actions in criminal proceedings within the digital environment.

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